

NEW INSIGHTS ON THE SYNERGISTIC REGULATION MECHANISM OF STRENGTHENING AND CORROSION RESISTANCE IN AL-ZN-MG-SC ALLOYS AGING TREATMENT

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This study investigates the influence of aging treatment temperature on the microstructure, mechanical properties, and corrosion resistance of Al-Zn-Mg-Sc alloy. The research findings indicate that aging treatment can effectively regulate the morphology of the intragranular and grain boundary precipitation phases of the Al-Zn-Mg-Sc alloy, leading to the formation of a dispersed, discontinuous nanometer η' complex phase structure within the matrix. This η' nanocomplex phase structure creates a high-density dispersion that obstructs dislocation movement, thereby enhancing the mechanical properties. Furthermore, the high-density, discontinuous distribution of nanometer phases formed within the grains and at the grain boundaries significantly mitigates the strong galvanic corrosion effect at the material's grain boundaries. This results in a reduced galvanic corrosion rate in the intergranular micro-regions, disrupts the continuous dissolution channels of intergranular corrosion, and substantially improves both the local corrosion resistance and intergranular corrosion resistance of the Al-Zn-Mg-Sc alloy.

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